

ECONOMIC IMPACT OF GREEN ECONOMY: LESSONS FROM FOREIGN COUNTRIES

Feruza Azamat qizi Bekmurodova

Senior teacher, PhD

University of world economy and diplomacy

Email: fbekmurodova7@gmail.com

Abstract. *The green economy has been the key driver of economic growth and sustainable development. It impacts the economy through job creation, emerging new industries, higher investment, and budget earnings. Due to these reasons, many countries are shifting towards a green economy from traditional industry. However, in order to achieve economic greenery, developing countries may face some difficulties. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the experience of the two main 2 Asian leaders of green transition: China and Singapore, by learning their strategies and how to implement them. The paper mainly focuses on comparing and creating policy recommendations for future emerging markets towards a green economy.*

Keywords: *green bonds, ESG, green finance, GDP share.*

ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ ВЛИЯНИЕ ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ: УРОКИ ЗАРУБЕЖНЫХ СТРАН

Ферузы Азамат кизи Бекмуродова

Старший преподаватель, кандидат наук

Университет мировой экономики и дипломатии

Электронная почта: fbekmurodova7@gmail.com

Аннотация. *Зеленая экономика является ключевым двигателем экономического роста и устойчивого развития. Она оказывает влияние на экономику посредством создания рабочих мест, появления новых отраслей, увеличения инвестиций и бюджетных поступлений. По этим причинам многие страны переходят от традиционной промышленности к зеленой экономике. Однако для достижения «зеленой» экономики развивающиеся страны могут столкнуться с некоторыми трудностями. Поэтому данное исследование направлено на анализ опыта двух ведущих азиатских стран в области «зеленого» перехода: Китая и Сингапура, путем изучения их стратегий и способов их реализации. В работе основное внимание уделяется сравнению и разработке рекомендаций по политике для будущих развивающихся рынков в направлении «зеленой» экономики.*

Ключевые слова: зеленые облигации, ESG, зеленое финансирование, доля ВВП.

YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING IQTISODIY TA’SIRI: XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDAN SABOQLAR

Feruza Azamat qizi Bekmurodova

Katta o‘qituvchi, PhD

Jahon iqtisodiyoti va diplomatiya universiteti

Elektron pochta: fbekmurodova7@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. *Yashil iqtisodiyot iqtisodiy o‘sish va barqaror rivojlanishning asosiy omili bo‘lib kelgan. U iqtisodiyotga ish o‘rinlarini yaratish, yangi sanoat tarmoqlarining paydo bo‘lishi, investitsiyalarning ko‘payishi va budget daromadlari orqali ta’sir qiladi. Shu sabablarga ko‘ra ko‘plab mamlakatlar an’anaviy sanoatdan yashil iqtisodiyotga o‘tmoqda. Biroq, iqtisodiy yashillikka erishish uchun rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar ba’zi qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishi mumkin. Shuning uchun, ushbu tadqiqot Osiyoning yashil o‘tishning asosiy 2 yetakchisi - Xitoy va Singapurning strategiyasini va ularni qanday amalga oshirishni o‘rganish orqali ularning tajribasini tahlil qilishga qaratilgan. Maqola asosan kelajakdagi rivojlanayotgan bozorlar uchun yashil iqtisodiyotga yo‘naltirilgan siyosat tavsiyalarini taqqoslash va yaratishga qaratilgan.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *yashil obligatsiyalar, ESG, yashil moliya, YaIM ulushi.*

INTRODUCTION

In today’s rapidly changing geopolitical world, countries are paying attention to the green economy, as it has become the driver of sustainable economic growth. One of the key reasons why many even oil-dependent countries are slowly changing towards a non-oil industry is that the green economy provides environmental sustainability through efficient resource use, reduction of carbon emissions, investment in green technologies, and, more importantly, is suitable for human health.

However, shifting towards a green economy is not something that can be achieved easily. Through steady and slow steps, it stimulates economic enhancement, leading to an increased number of green infrastructures, job creation in renewable energy industries, and investment in human health. On the other hand, it requires strong structural transformation, which may involve high costs in the short term, resulting in a high number of investments and budget earnings. Due to these reasons,

this paper aims to study the economic effects of the green economy through a comparative analysis of 3 economically different countries: China, Singapore, and Germany. All of their experience in the green economy is differently oriented, thus it will be analyzed to achieve a better understanding and possible outcomes for emerging markets.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many scholars debated about the main factors to measure the green economy. Some people believe a green economy is using renewable energy only; however, some prefer the term using it for carbon emission and its reduction. [7] Studies claim that using the green productivity index would show a better image of the green economy and how it's working currently for a country, especially China. [7] Some scholars researched about how the green economy can be distributed by region, showing the distribution inequality, particularly in provinces of China. [2] They claim that a green economy is efficient when it creates job opportunities, not only in city places but also in regional areas. Another paper focuses on how the digital economy affects the green economy, whether it is positive or negative, concluding with positive outcomes. [8]

Within works about Singapore, they are mainly based on how Singapore can achieve its 2030 plan, while considering possible effects. One of the papers claims that on this path, Singapore may have safety and health regulation issues, for investing more on green economy; however, it creates new green jobs within the country, debating its both positive and negative effects. [4] On the other hand, another paper shows the legal aspect of the strategy, analyzing its legal implications and environmental laws. [1]

Turkish scholars, who learned about Singapore’s green development, claim that it showed massive improvement regardless of resource shortage and high import dependency, providing useful insights from the country’s experience. [3] One of the impactful studies claims that, like China, in Singapore, there is also an issue of green urbanism. Greenery mainly focuses on cities, while island or rural areas are lacking behind. In order to build “The renewable city” or “Carbon neutral city,” the government should also focus on regions at the same amount. [5] Studies show how important it is to learn green economy in detail, which will be the main aim of the research.

METHODOLOGY

The paper mainly focuses on the experience of China and Singapore, using the comparison method. It also uses secondary data analysis, by analyzing main www.sharqjurnali.uz

green economy-related macroeconomic indicators, such as GDP share of green economy, and investments in the industry. Also, the research explains the ESG criteria, which are used to measure the sustainability of production or services by the government and companies. It provides a standard criteria method to scale companies’ activities. All statistical data are used based on reliable sources as well.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The concept of *green economy* is widely used, but narrowly defined. Many scholars represent it as investing in or utilizing only nature-friendly forms of energy. However, the term is broader than this narrow definition. A green economy is the type of economic activity that reduces the cost of living for consumers, decreases government expenses in the long term, and has a positive impact on the environment at the same time. Causing not only the enhancement of the environment, but also the health of the human population, many countries are shifting towards a green economy from a traditional one. The biggest example being China, the country has hugely invested into green economy for the past 4 years. Having the highest population and global trade, efficient resource allocation is one of the priorities for the country, leading to increased investment in green energy. On the other hand, the member of the European region, Germany, also leads in this industry with its green infrastructure; meanwhile, the representative of Asia, Singapore, is considered an innovation-driven economy. These countries represent different economic models: China as an industrial growth-driven economy, Germany as a developed sustainability leader, and Singapore as an innovation-driven green finance hub. Step by step, we will explore the economic path of these countries from a traditional to a green economy.

The main macroeconomic indicator for analyzing the current economic position of the green economy is the GDP share of the industry in percentage. Based on the table below, it is clear that China has the leading numbers, showing better economic earnings in the industry.

Table 1

The GDP share of the green economy (in percentage) [9]

Year	China	Singapore
2021	7–8%	3–4%
2022	9%	4%
2023	9–10%	4–5%
2024	10%	5%

2025	11.4%	5–6%
------	-------	------

Over the past 5 years, the amount of the green economy in GDP has been significant in both countries. It defies the strong stimulation of the green economy by the government. Especially China, having almost 12% of GDP in 2025, shows effective government policies. Compared to China, Singapore shows a steady amount of almost 3-6% for the past five years. The reason is that Singapore does not measure the green economy by GDP share; they mostly use the amount of green finances and bonds.

On the other hand, both countries heavily invest in a green transition to accelerate total shifting. Over the past years, China’s investment in industry started from \$500 bn, reaching almost 1 trillion in 2025. According to datasets, in the exact same year, over 90% of new investment growth came from clean energy in China.

Table 2

Total green investment (in \$bn) [9]

Year	China (USD bn)	Singapore (USD bn)
2021	500–550	10–15
2022	600–650	15–20
2023	850	20–25
2024	940	25–30
2025	1000 (est.)	30+

The table shows Singapore is also noticeably investing in the green economy, however the main difference is that the country mainly focuses on green finance and ESG methods.

Green finance - all money or loans directed into industries that cause sustainable development and nature-efficient industries. Singapore leads in green finance in the Asian region, with its unique way of measuring green loans and investments: ESG.

ESG criteria, which is used to decide where money goes to the economy, standing for followings:

E – environmental: it shows how a company impacts nature by carbon emissions, pollution, energy use, and waste management. The higher the nature-friendly products or activity, the better the chance of getting investment or loans.

S- Social: how companies in the industry treat people through work conditions, human rights, and customer safety.

G – Governance: the connection between the company and government, how it is managed, and what the response will be. It takes into account transparency, ethical behavior, and anti-corruption. The government supports green industries through the Energy Efficiency Fund and Resource Efficiency grants. It is enabling Singapore main green finance hub in the world, especially in Asia.

The main framework of Singapore for the industry is “Singapore Green Plan 2030”. The strategy is based on the following pillars: city in nature, energy reset, sustainable living, green economy, and resilient future. Within the strategy, Singapore is planning to achieve 80% of green buildings, the City in Nature concept, where people live within nature, not nature adopting their lifestyle. From children’s playgrounds to city bridges, the country intends to fully implement energy generated by human movement by reducing costs and oil imports. Another main green finance that is directed to the industry is green agriculture. As it is known that Singapore is highly dependent on the import of meat products, with a growing population, this causes a food shortage. The country is invested in laboratories, where they produce real edible meat 100% equal to chicken or beef. It reduces the high cost of imports, solves the problem of the shortage of livestock products, creates new employment opportunities, and improves human capital in the long term. These innovations show how 2 countries, regardless of their location in the Asian region, has 2 different green economy strategies.

CONCLUSION

An analysis of the economic effects of the green economy, using China and Singapore as case studies, shows that the transition to sustainable development is not only an imperative for the environment but it is also a key driver of economic development. Despite their differences in economic structures and natural resources, China and Singapore have shown that the transition to sustainable development can have significant economic effects, provided that there are policies to support such an economic transition.

For China, the green economy is a key driver of the country’s economic performance, with the green economy’s contribution to the country’s GDP increasing significantly in recent years, accounting for a majority of the total economic growth. Through massive investments in renewable energy, electric cars, and clean technologies, China has developed a globally competitive industry, creating new job opportunities for its citizens, which in turn has improved the country’s balance of trade. This, therefore, shows that the transition to sustainable development in an industrialized country can be a key driver of economic growth.

On the other hand, Singapore represents a different model of green economic development, in which economic growth is fueled by innovation, efficiency, and financial services, rather than by large-scale, resource-intensive industries. Through the development of green finance, the implementation of carbon pricing, and investments in sustainable infrastructure, Singapore has managed to successfully established itself as a regional investment hub for sustainable investment. This, therefore, confirms that even resource-constrained economies can benefit from the economic effects of a green transition through the development of high-value services and innovation.

From the analysis above, the following recommendations can be applied for emerging countries:

- Prioritizing green investment in the long term: high costs of spending may cause some inflation, or can be seen as higher in numbers, but in the long term, it can provide qualified capital increase and better earnings in the industry;
- Developing government policy frameworks: showing main points to be done, eliminating what it lacks, and what to focus more on, enables effective government policy and strategy, such as the Green Singapore plan 2030.
- Supporting and promoting: by explaining more about green energy, people and industries will understand the concept and its importance. When supported in even rural areas, it will cause regional development of the economy as well.
- Focusing on green technologies: applying human action-generated energy mechanisms will reduce traditional energy dependency incredibly.
- Green finance system: actively using ESG criteria to measure companies will stimulate them to shift towards a green economy faster and better.

If the recommendations above are implemented, developing countries may not face difficulties in the industry, by increasing income, investment, and reducing costs for people and the environment.

REFERENCES:

1. Chng, K., & Ong, K. W. (2021). The Singapore Green Plan 2030: Analysing its implications on law and the legal industry in Singapore. *Environmental Law Review*, 23(4), 336-343.
2. Hongtao Yi, Yuan Liu, Green economy in China: Regional variations and policy drivers, *Global Environmental Change*, Volume 31, 2015, Pages 11-19, ISSN 0959-3780, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2014.12.001>

3. Karabulut, S. (2024). Industrial Policy and Green Growth in a Small Island Economy: The Case of Singapore. *Industrial Policy*, 4(2), 75-89. <https://doi.org/10.61192/indpol.1485611>
4. Lim, Wei Xiang MBBS, MPH (OM)1; Tan, Mei Ling Licia MB BCh BAO (Hons), FAMS (OM)1; Teo, Tzu Li Sylvia MBBS, MMED (OM)2; Gan, Wee Hoe MBBS, FAMS3; Wong, Shiu Hong Joshua MBBS, FAMS1. The Singapore Green Plan 2030: occupational health hazards in the Singapore green economy. *Singapore Medical Journal* 66(4): p 181-189, April 2025. | DOI: 10.4103/singaporemedj.SMJ-2024-121
5. Newman, P. (2010). Green Urbanism and Its Application to Singapore. *Environment and Urbanization ASIA*, 1(2), 149-170.
6. Subramaniam Y, Loganathan N (2024), "Does green finance affect renewable energy development in Singapore?". *Journal of Asian Business and Economic Studies*, Vol. 31 No. 3 pp. 162–174, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABES-02-2023-0052>
7. Wei Pan, Wulin Pan, Cheng Hu, Haiting Tu, Cheng Zhao, Dongyang Yu, Jianwu Xiong, Guanwen Zheng, Assessing the green economy in China: An improved framework, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 209, 2019, Pages 680-691, ISSN 0959-6526, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.10.267>.
8. Wang, C., Liu, T., Du, D., Zhu, Y., Zheng, Z., & Li, H. (2024). Impact of the Digital Economy on the Green Economy: Evidence from China. *Sustainability*, 16(21), 9217. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16219217>
9. Website: Carbon Brief: <https://www.carbonbrief.org/analysis-clean-energy-drove-more-than-a-third-of-chinas-gdp-growth-in-2025/>